

Celsianol, A Novel Sterol from *Celsia coromandeliana* Vahl*

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A new sterol, celsianol, has been isolated from *Celsia coromandeliana* Vahl. and its structure has been established as stigmasta- $\Delta^{5,9(11)}$ -dien-3 β -ol.

Celsia coromandeliana Vahl¹. (N.O. Scrophulariaceae), a shrub widely growing throughout the plains of India and Ceylon, is reported to be effective in skin eruptions², fevers and dysentery³, etc. Since no work appears to have been carried out on this important plant, a systematic chemical examination was, therefore, undertaken and a hitherto unreported sterol, provisionally named as celsianol (I), has been isolated and characterised as stigmasta- $\Delta^{5,9(11)}$ -diene-3 β -ol.

Sterol (I), was isolated by column chromatography of the nonsaponifiable fractions of petroleum-ether extract of the plant on alumina. It has the molecular formula $C_{29}H_{48}O$ (M^+412), m.p. 166–68° and $[\alpha]_D^{28} + 3.1^\circ$. This substance gave positive Liebermann-Burchard⁴ test for sterol and a positive tetranitromethane reaction for unsaturation. The I.R. spectrum (KBr) showing peaks at 3401, 1043 and 1034 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of hydroxyl group. The presence of double bond is suggested by a weak absorption band at 1656 cm^{-1} and that these double bonds are tri-substituted, is indicated by sharp absorption band^{5,6} at 840 cm^{-1} .

* Ph.D. thesis, A. R. Chowdhury, Lucknow University, Lucknow, 1969.

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On acetylation with acetic anhydride-pyridine, it yielded an acetate, $C_{31}H_{50}O_2$, m.p. 172-73°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 7.0^\circ$. The I.R. spectrum indicated peaks at 1736 (C=O) and 1248 cm^{-1} (C-O-C). On benzylation with benzoyl chloride-pyridine it yielded a benzoate, m.p. 177°, $[\alpha]_D^{28} + 11.1^\circ$. Jones' oxidation⁷ of this substance afforded a ketone celsianone (III), m.p. 162-63°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 12.0^\circ$. The ketone has no U.V. maxima above 212 $m\mu$. The I.R. spectrum of celsianone showed absorption band at 1712 cm^{-1} suggesting the presence of C=O group in a six membered ring (unconjugated).

Integration of the proton signals of the N.M.R. spectrum of celsianol confirms the presence of 48 protons in the molecule. Of these 48 hydrogen atoms 18 are present as six methyl groups. The presence of six methyl groups in a C_{29} molecules leaves no doubt about celsianol being a steroid^{8,9}. Celsianol has two ethylenic protons, which give rise to complex multiplet centred at 4.85 τ . The proton on the carbon attached to the hydroxyl function ($>CHOH$) is clearly seen as a diffused multiplet centred at 6.37 τ . This signal shifts to down field at 5.22 τ in the spectrum of celsianol acetate and the down field shifts of 70 cps is always observed with 3-hydroxy steroids. Saturated side chain was indicated by the appearance of a signal for one methyl group (C_{18}) at a comparative low field¹⁰ (9.43 τ) in the N.M.R. spectrum of celsianol. The position of C_{18} and C_{19} methyl groups are at 9.43 and 9.20 τ respectively. The positions of C_{18} and C_{19} methyl groups in celsianol acetate are at 9.46 and 9.20 τ respectively.

The M_D values of celsianol and celsianol acetate are +54.0 and +32.0 respectively. The Δ_1 value for celsianol is, therefore, -22. This is in agreement with the proposed 3 β -OH structure for celsianol^{11,12}.

The mass spectrum of celsianol has a molecular ion peak at m/e 412 which provides further evidence for the presence of a $C_{10}H_{21}$ saturated side chain by showing intense peak at m/e 271 ($M^+ - C_{10}H_{21}$) and m/e 229 ($M^+ - C_{10}H_{21} - 42$). The peak at m/e 229 shows a normal tetracyclic steroid skeleton^{13,14} with a saturated side chain attached at position C_{17} , placing the two double bonds and the hydroxyl function in the tetracyclic moiety. Absence of M-72 peak in the mass spectrum of celsianol is indicative of Δ^5 unsaturation¹⁵. The mass spectrum of celsianol acetate shows the expected molecular ion peak at m/e 454 and peak

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at m/e 394 corresponds to the loss of CH_3COOH . This confirms the presence of one hydroxyl group in celsianol¹⁶. The mass spectrum of celsianone has the molecular ion peak at m/e 410 and the base peak occurred at m/e 269.

The compound I, its acetate (II) and ketone (III) showed no U.V. maxima above $212 \text{ m}\mu$. The lack of conjugation in U.V. of the compound as well as these derivatives indicated absence of double bond in ring A. This in conjunction with the presence of two vinylic proton (N.M.R. spectrum) led to the conclusion that two tri-substituted nonconjugated double bonds are present. Assuming $3\beta\text{-OH}$, Δ^5 -structure for I, the other trisubstituted double bond should be at either $\Delta^{9(11)}$ or $\Delta^{14(15)}$.

The presence of $\Delta^{9(11)}$ double bond is indicated by a positive Tertelli Jaffé test¹⁷. The positions of Δ^5 and $\Delta^{9(11)}$ double bonds were proved by the preparation of Δ^7 ketone (IV) by treating celsianol acetate with 1.08 *N* chromic acid, having U.V. maxima at $252 \text{ m}\mu$ indicating that ketone is formed at C_7 with migration of $\Delta^{9(11)}$ double bond to more stable $\Delta^{8(9)}$ position. The position of Δ^5 double bond was proved by isomerizing celsianone (III) with methanolic hydrogen chloride into a Δ^4 ketone having α, β conjugation as shown by U.V. maxima at $242 \text{ m}\mu$ (Σ , 15,600).

The carbon skeleton of celsianol was firmly established by the hydrogenation of celsianol in the presence of platinum oxide and ethyl acetate to give dihydro derivative, $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$ (M^+ 412), m.p. 148° , $[\alpha]_D^{23} +15^\circ$, which still gives a positive Tortelli Jaffé test showing presence of unreducible $\Delta^{9(11)}$ double bond. This observation was further supported by N.M.R. spectrum of dihydro compound, showing the presence of only one vinyl proton centred at 4.92τ . This indicated that the hydrogenation occurs at easily reducible Δ^5 double bond while $\Delta^{9(11)}$ double bond still remains intact. The above dihydro compound was acetylated with acetic anhydride-pyridine. This on further hydrogenation with platinum oxide in acetic acid gave an isomeric compound, which when hydrolysed with 5% NaOH gave a product identical with α -spinastanol¹⁸ (stigmast- $\Delta^{8(14)}$ -ene- 3β -ol) in m.p., m.m.p. and superimposable I.R. spectra. This fixes the stereochemistry of celsianol (I) as stigmasta- $\Delta^{5,9(11)}$ -diene- 3β -ol.

Celsianol, as far as we are aware, is the first authentic sample of naturally occurring stigmast $\Delta^{5,9(11)}$ diene and its isolation precludes its formation by rearrangement from a naturally occurring $\Delta^{8(9)}$ or $\Delta^{8(14)}$ precursor. It is interesting to note that nature has provided

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so many thermodynamically stable sterols as compared to the more stable $\Delta^8(9)$ or $\Delta^8(14)$ sterols. Recently, the isolation of two new sterols, stigmasta- $\Delta^7,24(28)$ -diene- 3β -ol¹⁹, and stigmasta- $\Delta^8(14),22$ -diene- 3β -ol¹⁰ isomeric with celsianol has been reported.

EXPERIMENTAL

The m.p.'s are uncorrected, the U.V. spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 202 automatic recording spectrophotometer in ethanol. All optical rotations were determined in chloroform. The I.R. spectra were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer Infra-cord 137B and the N.M.R. spectra were taken in a Varian A-60 in CDCl_3 solution with T.M.S. as internal standard.

Isolation of celsianol : The air dried powdered plant (8 kg.) was extracted exhaustively with 95% ethanol and the combined extract (60 ml.) was concentrated below 48° under reduced pressure to 4 litres. The residue was extracted with petroleum-ether (60–80°) and the combined extract concentrated to a greenish oily mass (30 g.). This extract was saponified with 5% alcoholic sodium hydroxide (200 ml.), cooled and the non-saponifiable material, then extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water which on concentration gave a brown mass (13 g.). This was chromatographed over activated Brockman-alumina (500 g.), using benzene-chloroform (4 : 1) as eluant affording a colourless solid (1.2 g.). Crystallisation from methanol-chloroform, yielded celsianol m.p. 166–68°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 13.1^\circ$, γ_{\max} , 3401 (OH stretching) 1043 and 1034 cm^{-1} (C–O), 840 cm^{-1} (trisubstituted double bond) (Found : C, 84.40; H, 11.52; $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.46; H, 11.65%).

Celsianol acetate : Celsianol (0.1 g.) was treated with acetic anhydride (3 ml.), dry pyridine (3 ml.) and left overnight at room temperature. The product was poured into ice cold water. The precipitate was filtered, dried and then crystallised with methanol-chloroform as needles, m.p. 172–73°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 7.0^\circ$, γ_{\max} 1736 ($\text{CH}_3\text{C} = \text{O}$) and 1248 cm^{-1} (C–O–C) (Found : C, 82.01; H, 11.02. $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 81.93; H, 11.01%).

Celsianol benzoate : Celsianol (0.10 g.) was treated with pyridine (2 ml.) and benzoyl chloride (2 ml.). The mixture was heated over water bath for 1 hr. The product was extracted with ether and the extract was washed successively with dil. hydrochloric acid, water, 5% sodium bicarbonate, water and dried over sodium sulphate. Removal of solvent gave a solid which was crystallised from methanol as shiny plates (0.085 g.), m.p. 177°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 11.1^\circ$, γ_{\max} 1724 cm^{-1} (C–O stretching for benzoate) (Found : C, 83.68; H, 10.10. $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 83.72; H, 10.08%).

Celsianone : Celsianol (0.1 g.) was dissolved in dry acetone at 20° and 8 N chromic acid (Jones reagent) added dropwise until a permanent orange brown colouration obtained, indicating that the oxidation was complete. After 10 min. the reaction mixture was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution, and dried. The residue on removal of solvent was crystallized from methanol to give celsianone (0.065 g.), m.p. 162–63°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 12.0^\circ$, ν_{\max} 1712 cm^{-1} (unconjugated ketone in a six membered ring) (Found : C, 84.80; H, 11.16. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.87; H, 11.21%).

Isomerization of celsianone into iso-celsianone (Isomerization of Δ^5 to Δ^4 double bond): Celsianone (0.03 g.) was treated with methanolic hydrogen chloride (5 ml; 2%) and the mixture was refluxed for 4 hrs. The product diluted with water was extracted with ether to give isocelsianone, m.p. 168°, λ_{\max} 242m μ (Σ , 15600) (Found : C, 84.61; H, 11.19. $C_{29}H_{46}O$ requires C, 84.87; H, 11.21%).

Chromic acid oxidation of celsianol acetate : Celsianol acetate (0.1 g.) in glacial acetic acid (62 ml.) was added to chromium trioxide solution in acetic acid (1.08 N, 1.25 ml.) and the mixture left overnight at room temperature. Unreacted chromic acid was decomposed by methanol and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was extracted with ether and the ether extract washed with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution, water and dried. The residue after removal of ether, was crystallised from methanol-acetone (3 : 1) mixture as white needles, m.p. 185°, $[\alpha]_D^{23} + 50.0^\circ$, γ_{\max} 1735 ($COCH_3$) and 1664 cm^{-1} ($C=O$); λ_{\max} 252 m μ (Σ , 7027) (Found : C, 79.38; H, 10.11. $C_{31}H_{48}O_3$ requires, C, 79.48, H, 10.25%).

Dihydrocelsianol (Hydrogenation of celsianol) : Celsianol (0.1 g.) hydrogenated with Adam's catalyst (0.01 g.) in ethyl acetate in an atmosphere of hydrogen for 6 hrs. gave a dihydro compound (0.078 g.), m.p. 148°, $[\alpha]_D^{29} + 15^\circ$. (Found : C, 83.98; H, 12.04. $C_{29}H_{50}O$ requires C, 84.06; H, 12.07%).

Dihydrocelsianol acetate : The above hydrogenated product (0.05 g.) was treated with acetic anhydride (2 ml.), dry pyridine (2 ml.) and allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The product was poured in ice cold water and the precipitate was filtered, dried and then crystallised from methanol-chloroform as plates (0.039 g.), m.p. 156°, $[\alpha]_D^{24} + 13.0^\circ$ (Found : C, 81.10; H, 11.47. $C_{31}H_{52}O_2$ requires C, 81.57; H, 11.40%).

Hydrogenation (Isomerization of Dihydrocelsianol acetate into stigmast- $\Delta^{8(14)}$ -ene-3 β -acetate) : Dihydrocelsianol acetate (0.025 g.) was hydrogenated in presence of Adam's catalyst in acetic acid (5 ml.) under an atmosphere of hydrogen for 6 hrs. The solution was filtered and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with 5% sodium bicarbonate, water and dried. The residue after removal of ether, crystallised from methanol to give stigmast- $\Delta^{8(14)}$ -ene-3 β -acetate, m.p. 117°, $[\alpha]_D^{23} + 15^\circ$ (Found : C, 81.08; H, 11.45. $C_{31}H_{52}O_2$ requires C, 81.57; H, 11.40%).

α -spinastanol (Hydrolysis of stigmast- $\Delta^{8(14)}$ -ene-3 β -acetate) : The stigmast- $\Delta^{8(14)}$ -ene-3 β -acetate (0.02 g.) was hydrolysed with 5% alcoholic sodium hydroxide (5 ml.) for 3 hrs. and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water and dried. Removal of solvent afforded a residue which was crystallised from methanol-chloroform to give stigmast- $\Delta^{8(14)}$ -ene-3 β -ol, m.p. 114.5°, $[\alpha]_D^{28} + 18^\circ$ (Found : C, 84.10; H, 11.98. Calc. for $C_{29}H_{50}O$ C, 84.06; H, 12.07%).

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